

DEPENDENCE OF CLINICAL MANIFESTATIONS OF FOOD ALLERGY ON THE TYPE OF DIET IN YOUNG CHILDREN LIVING IN THE ARAL SEA REGION

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Objective: to determine the features of the clinical course of food allergy in young children in the Khorezm region who are on various types of feeding in order to develop optimal prevention and treatment.

Material and methods: 70 children with allergic diseases were examined in order to identify changes in their allergic system. The average age of the patients was 1-5 years. All child patients underwent inpatient treatment at the sharioiti Multidisciplinary Children's Hospital of Khorezm region. All child patients underwent such examinations as an objective examination, clinical and biochemical blood tests and immunoglobulin determination.

Results: Today, food allergy is considered as a multifactorial pathology, a number of genetic and environmental factors play a role in its occurrence and development, which is the cause of various clinical manifestations of food allergies. However, in general, the direct causes of the increase in the spread of food allergies remain unclear. As a result of determining the features of regional clinical rejection of food allergies in young children, it was noticed that food allergies in children of the Khorezm region manifest themselves in gastrointestinal and skin forms. As a result of determining the dependence of food allergies in children on the type of diet, it was noticed that children with artificial nutrition have imbalances in the form of coronary heart disease and Quincke's edema, gastrointestinal tract with mixed nutrition and atopic dermatitis with natural nutrition.

Keywords: *food allergy, natural and artificial feeding, immune response, ecology.*

Topicality

Currently, there is an increase in the number of allergic diseases worldwide, comparable to the scale of the epidemic [13, 12]. The World Health Organization considers the problem of diagnosis and treatment of allergic diseases to be one of the priorities of public health. The frequency of food allergies reaches 6-8% in children in the first years of life [10, 11].

Allergic diseases in a child, regardless of the form of clinical manifestations, worsen the quality of life of the whole family. In addition, there is an increase in the economic costs of treatment, including pharmacotherapy, topical medications, and specialized food products [13].

Obviously, the search for effective measures for the prevention and treatment of allergic diseases is extremely relevant [9,15,].

An important component of the comprehensive treatment of food allergies is pathogenetically based diet therapy, based on the clinical form and stage of the allergic process, the characteristics of food sensitization, physiological needs for macro- and micronutrients, and the nutritional status of the child.

In this regard, diagnostic measures should be aimed both at assessing the functional state of the organs and systems of the child's body, the nature of the immune response, and at identifying causally significant food allergens [2,9,8].

In infants who are on mixed or artificial feeding, the success of diet therapy largely depends on the correct choice of a specialized basic food product.

Currently, a wide range of therapeutic mixtures based on protein hydrolysates has been developed. The composition features of each of the proposed mixtures determine its advantages and disadvantages for a particular child with food allergies. Widespread chemicalization of the environment and everyday life, increased radiation background, socio-psychological stresses, changes in food quality contributed to the formation of secondary immunodeficiency among other pathological conditions [Gerasimov A.A., 2013].

The clinical consequence of this is the widespread occurrence of allergic diseases such as bronchial asthma, pollinosis, and food allergies [Razikova I.S., 2001; Nazarov A.A., 2009]. As a rule, the diagnosis of "food allergy" is made on the basis of a causal relationship between food intake and the development of clinical symptoms of its intolerance [1].

According to domestic and foreign researchers, the prevalence of food allergies varies widely – from 0.1 to 50%. Such a wide range of data on the prevalence of food allergies confirms the fact that there are no reliable methods for diagnosing food allergies. More often, food allergies are observed in children, adults, as a rule, suffer from it since childhood.

The incidence of food allergies in children under 3 years of age is 4-6%. For 80-90% of children with food allergies, causal allergens are found in a small number of products – these are eggs, milk, peanuts, soy, wheat, fish [2,10]. Among children of the first year of life, allergy to cow's milk proteins occurs in 0.5-1.5% of infants who are naturally fed, and in 2-7% of children who are artificially fed [5,8].

Studies conducted in the Aral Sea region have shown the presence of some organochlorine pesticides, heavy metal salts, especially toxic dioxins in the blood of pregnant women, umbilical cord blood and breast milk [10,15].

Thus, it is currently relevant to improve the diagnostic approach and optimize early diagnosis, treatment and prevention of sick children with food allergies, and solving these problems will improve patient management tactics and reduce the incidence rate.

Objective: to determine the features of the clinical course of food allergy in young children in the Khorezm region who are on various types of feeding in order to develop optimal prevention and treatment.

Material and methods: 70 children with allergic diseases were examined in order to identify changes in their allergic system. The average age of the children was 1-5 years old. All children received inpatient treatment at the multidisciplinary children's hospital of the Khorezm region. The control group consisted of 60 healthy children of the same age who did not have chronic foci of infection and did not suffer from allergic diseases.

The clinical characteristics of children with food allergies were carried out taking into account anamnestic data, the main, concomitant diagnoses, as well as background conditions. The basis for the diagnosis were: complaints, anamnesis data, results of general clinical and laboratory studies.

There were two directions in the diagnosis of food allergies. At the first stage of the diagnosis of food allergy, anamnestic data and clinical symptoms of the disease were evaluated. At the second stage, causally significant factors of food allergy were identified.

The results of our own research: The results of the study showed that the most common forms of food allergy in children of early childhood.

A gastrointestinal form was found in the Khorezm region, which occurred in 34.2% and was accompanied by abdominal pain, flatulence, constipation, unstable stools, etc. Atopic dermatitis occurred in 32.5% and was accompanied by itching and skin rash of varying intensity. Respiratory allergosis in 27.3%, acute urticaria and Quincke's edema in 6% of children. Atopic dermatitis in 36.6%, gastrointestinal allergy in 21.7% of children, respiratory allergy in 15.0% of children.

We also analyzed the feeding of young children. The examined children of the Khorezm region were naturally fed by 22.2%, mixed-fed by 33.3% of children and artificially fed by 44.4% of children.

As shown by our research in the Khorezm region - with mixed feeding. Interesting data were obtained when collecting the allergeoanamnesis of children in the Khorezm region with food allergies: hereditary burden was noted in 38%, and on the maternal side twice as often as on the paternal side, allergic diathesis - 25%, focal infections - 24%, pregnancy toxicosis in 26% of mothers of sick children.

The most common symptom of the gastrointestinal form was abdominal pain in 75% of patients who had different localization, intensity and duration.

Abdominal pain was often persistent, but there were also episodic (up to 3-4 times a week).

The change in appetite was noted in the form of anorexia, decrease and selectivity. At the same time, impaired appetite was accompanied by dyspeptic manifestations - belching, regurgitation, vomiting in 59.1%.

In children of the Khorezm region, manifestations of atopic dermatitis (36.6%) were generalized. There were no skin rashes near the mouth and on the eyelids.

A characteristic clinical feature was also the "geographical language" indicating hyperplasia. Rashes were more often localized on the front and back of the neck, the inner surface of the thighs.

Skin rashes, unlike eczema, did not have vesiculation and eczema "wells". Excoriation was noted on the skin due to constant scratching, the children were characterized by nervousness, tearfulness and hysteria.

Urticaria and Quincke's edema in children of the Khorezm region were found in 26.7% of patients. Complaints were about the appearance of edema of different sizes, surrounded by erythema, in various parts of the body. The rash, of various shapes and sizes, was accompanied by itchy skin. Angioedema is more often observed on the eyelids, lips and scrotum.

Clinical manifestations of respiratory allergies (allergic rhinitis, laryngitis, bronchitis,) were: itching and burning in the nose, nasopharynx, eyes; discharge of mucous fluid from the nose; lacrimation; cough, etc. We analyzed the age-related onset of food allergies in children. Thus, clinical manifestations of gastrointestinal allergy debuted mainly during the first three months of life in 63.9% of cases, and by the end of the first year of life - in only 3.4% of patients.

All children from these groups had an increased level of sensitization to cow's milk proteins. The combination of urticaria with the gastrointestinal form was noted in 16.4% of children, in whose clinic dyspeptic disorder and the appearance of polymorphic rashes on various parts of the body were also observed, which were accompanied by severe itching, and they were in the form of localized or generalized forms.

Atopic dermatitis combined with respiratory allergies was found in 10.2% of children who had the above-mentioned changes and respiratory ones in the form of allergic bronchitis, allergic laryngitis. These children had a dry cough, persistent runny nose and hoarseness of voice, shortness of breath, and in some patients signs of suffocation. These symptoms were observed at the age of 2-3 years and especially after taking sweets, eggs, honey. Urticaria, Quincke's edema in combination with respiratory manifestations were observed in 6.8% of children.

In these children, the respiratory allergy clinic was more severe and had significant respiratory and swallowing disorders, and fever was also noted.

The basis of therapy for children with food allergies was diet therapy and an elimination diet was prescribed. Also in the diet of a child suffering from food allergies, it is necessary to reduce the amount of salt and sugar and completely eliminate all seasonings.

Conclusion: As a result of scientific examinations in children living in the Khorezm region, a common form of allergic reactions from the gastrointestinal tract was observed, in children - atopic dermatitis and swelling of the nodule. The revealed changes indicate the relevance of studying the course of allergic diseases in children living in this region, taking into account the climatic, ecological and social characteristics of the island territory, as well as the need for more in-depth further research.

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